

Modelling the effect of anisotropy in gas injection tests on clays using zero-thickness interface elements

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Abstract:

Clay-rich materials are often chosen as geological formation and/or engineered barriers to isolate radioactive waste in deep geological disposal facilities (GDF). A significant amount of gas will be produced in the GDF over its lifetime. If the gas dissipation rate is lower than the gas production rate, gas pressure will build up, which could possibly jeopardize the integrity and performance of the barriers.

Among the different factors affecting gas migration in clay materials, the anisotropy of material properties is expected to play a major role. In a recent study, Gonzalez-Blanco [1] used an oedometer cell to perform gas injection tests on undisturbed Boom clay samples with bedding planes parallel and normal to the direction of the gas flow, in order to assess the influence of the orientation of the bedding on the hydro-mechanical response of the material. The results showed that the samples with bedding planes normal to the direction of gas flow underwent higher expansion than the samples with bedding planes parallel to the direction of flow, indicating that the gas pathways develop more easily along the bedding planes. This phenomenon becomes more obvious as the gas injection rate is increased.

With the purpose of investigating the hydro-mechanical mechanisms underlying the observed behaviour, a series of numerical simulations were performed using LAGAMINE, and a fully coupled Pneumo-Hydro-Mechanical (PHM) formulation. The bulk clay material is represented using coupled Mechanical-Water-Air-Temperature (MWAT) continuum elements, while bedding planes are explicitly represented using new zero-thickness interface elements (PHMI elements) recently proposed by some of the authors elsewhere [2].

In this presentation, the results obtained are discussed, as well as the suitability of the PHMI elements for representing bedding planes in clay formations.

References:

- [1] Gonzalez-Blanco, L. (2017). Gas Migration in Deep Argillaceous Formations. Boom Clay and Indurated Clays. PhD thesis, Barcelona, Spain. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya.
- [2] Liaudat, J., Dieudonné, A. C., Vardon, P.J. (2022). Modelling gas fracturing in saturated clay using triple-node zero-thickness interface elements. Under Review